

Enhancing Trace DNA Recovery from Disposable Face Masks: Insights from the COVID-19 Era and Beyond

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Key points

- **Superior Performance of Minitapes:** SceneSafe Fast™ minitapes (MT) demonstrated significantly higher efficiency in trace DNA recovery from disposable surgical face masks compared to Copan cotton swabs (CS), yielding more DNA and producing more complete DNA profiles.
- **Statistical Findings:** Minitapes recovered a mean DNA concentration of 0.41 ng/μL, compared to 0.17 ng/μL for cotton swabs, with a significantly greater proportion of full single (FS) and full mixed (FM) profiles ($p < 0.05$).
- **Practical Forensic Applications:** The adhesive properties of minitapes make them particularly effective for small or porous surfaces like face masks, offering an efficient and reliable alternative to traditional swabbing in forensic casework.

Abstract

Trace DNA plays a pivotal role in forensic investigations, serving as a critical tool for linking suspects to criminal activities. During the COVID-19 pandemic, disposable face masks emerged as key items of forensic interest, particularly in cases where suspects used them to conceal their identities. This study evaluates the efficiency of two trace DNA collection methodologies—cotton swabbing and tapelifting—for recovering DNA from face masks. Samples were collected from 50 masks worn by suspects in robbery cases, utilizing the Copan cotton swab (150C) and the SceneSafe Fast™ minitape (K545). Statistical analysis revealed that minitapes (MT) significantly outperformed cotton swabs (CS), yielding higher DNA concentrations (mean MT: 0.41 ng/μL, CS: 0.17 ng/μL; $p < 0.05$) and recovering more complete DNA profiles, including full single (FS) and full mixed (FM) profiles ($p < 0.05$). These findings highlight the superior efficiency of MT, particularly for recovering trace DNA from small or fabric-like surfaces. The study underscores the importance of selecting optimal collection methods in forensic investigations, especially for modern evidence types such as face masks. Recommendations include the routine adoption of minitapes in casework involving face masks and further research into their efficacy on other mask types and under varied environmental conditions. This research offers valuable insights to refine trace DNA recovery strategies, enhancing the reliability of forensic evidence.

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1 Introduction

The Trace or Touch DNA represents a critical type of genetic evidence frequently encountered at crime scenes, serving as an essential tool for linking suspects to criminal activities [1-6]. This form of DNA evidence is typically retrieved from everyday surfaces such as tools, door handles, and clothing [2,7-9]. However, the utility of Touch DNA presents inherent challenges distinct from those associated with conventional biological samples. These challenges stem from various factors, including the composition of the surface [10-11], environmental conditions [12-14], collection methodologies [10-11,15-17], collection techniques [18-23] (e.g., the amount of wetting reagents applied, the number of lifts performed with adhesive tapes, etc.), and extraction procedures [2,4,12,24-25]. Each of these factors significantly impacts the quantity and quality of recovered DNA.

Studies have demonstrated that the choice of collection method—whether using cotton swabs, nylon swabs, or adhesive tapes—plays a pivotal role in the efficiency of trace DNA recovery. The effectiveness of each method varies depending on the type of surface being sampled [10-11]. For example, cotton and nylon swabs are particularly efficient at recovering DNA from non-porous surfaces such as glass or plastic [10,19], while tapelifting has proven more effective for porous surfaces like clothing [26-31]. Beyond these conventional approaches, innovative techniques have been developed to optimize DNA recovery from challenging surfaces. These include dual recovery methods combining cotton swabs and microFLOQ® swabs for direct amplification, microbial wet-vacuum systems, and advanced chemical decontaminants [21,32-33]. Collectively, these advancements reflect the ongoing evolution of forensic methodologies. Additionally, variability in DNA recovery associated with substrate types and environmental conditions has been well-documented, further emphasizing the need for method-specific optimizations [34-37].

The COVID-19 pandemic in 2020 and 2021 introduced a new class of forensic evidence: face masks. During this period, face masks became prominent items submitted for examination to the Biology and DNA Section of the General Department of Forensic Science and Criminology at Dubai Police. Even beyond the pandemic, their use persisted in burglary cases, as suspects commonly employed masks to obscure their identities from CCTV cameras. This shift in criminal behavior presented

unique challenges for forensic investigations, necessitating innovative approaches to recover trace DNA and other biological residues from face masks. These advancements were critical for identifying perpetrators despite their attempts to remain anonymous. The adaptability of forensic methodologies at Dubai Police has played a key role in addressing these evolving crime patterns, showcasing the importance of integrating technological expertise and innovation to overcome modern investigative challenges [38]. This trend underscores the necessity of advancing forensic science techniques to meet the demands of shifting criminal behaviors.

Historically, forensic analysts primarily utilized cotton swabs to collect trace DNA from face masks, leaving the efficacy of tapelifting unexplored. However, specialized adhesive tapes have shown promise in enhancing DNA yields under specific conditions [26,29,39-41], such as when sampling from porous or fabric-like surfaces, small defined areas of fabric, or when minimizing the transfer of PCR inhibitors is critical. These conditions also include cases where there is a need to recover both DNA and other trace evidence, such as fingerprints. These methods offer a compelling alternative to address the challenges unique to forensic casework involving face masks. Consequently, the present study investigates the impact of collection methodology—specifically comparing cotton swabbing and tapelifting—on the recovery of trace DNA from Disposable Surgical Face Masks, which were mostly blue and white and composed of polypropylene and non-woven fabric.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 DNA recovery

For this study, two collection tools were selected to evaluate trace DNA recovery from disposable face masks: the Copan cotton swab (150C, abbreviated as CS) and the SceneSafe Fast™ minitape (K545, abbreviated as MT). Each tool was utilized under standardized conditions to ensure a fair comparison, including consistent application pressure, defined sampling areas, and adherence to manufacturer-recommended protocols for their use.

Prior to use, the CS was moistened with 100 µL of sterile distilled water using a precise plastic spray bottle technique [2,18,23]. The swab was then applied to the mask surface with medium pressure, rotating throughout the process to maximize DNA

collection. In contrast, the MT required no preparatory steps and was directly applied. To optimize DNA recovery, each MT was pressed and lifted from the designated mask area a total of 16 times [42].

The study involved the collection of 100 samples from 50 used face masks, which were submitted as evidence in robbery cases. For consistent comparison, both the CS and MT were used on the same mask. The inner right half of each mask (facing the wearer's face) was sampled using the CS, while the inner left half (also facing the wearer's face) was sampled using the MT (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1. This figure demonstrates the sampling strategy used to compare two trace DNA collection methods from disposable face masks. The mask surface was divided into two sections: the inner right half was sampled using the Copan cotton swab (CS), while the inner left half was sampled using the SceneSafe Fast™ minitape (MT). The CS was moistened with sterile distilled water before being applied with consistent pressure and rotation to collect biological material, while the MT was pressed and lifted systematically 16 times without requiring prior preparation. This dual-sampling approach ensured a direct comparison of the efficiency and effectiveness of each method in recovering trace DNA.

2.2 DNA Extraction and Amplification

Samples collected using the Copan cotton swabs (CS) and SceneSafe Fast™ minitapes (MT) were processed with the PrepFiler Express™ Forensic DNA Extraction Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific), utilizing a Tecan robot for automated liquid handling. To ensure comparability, the entire surface of the swab head was utilized, while the lower adhesive portion of the minitape—the part used for collection and equivalent in size to the sampled area on the mask—was processed for DNA extraction, with a final elution volume of 50 µL. DNA quantification was performed using the Qiagen Investigator Quantiplex Pro Quantification Kit and the QuantStudio 5 Real-Time PCR (qPCR) system, analyzed with HID Real-Time PCR Analysis Software v1.3, adhering to the manufacturer's protocols.

DNA amplification was carried out using the GlobalFiler™ PCR Amplification Kit on an ABI GeneAmp® 9700 PCR System (Thermo Fisher Scientific) with 29 cycles, following the kit's recommended protocol. The amplified DNA was size-separated and analyzed using an ABI 3500 Genetic Analyzer (Thermo Fisher Scientific). The injection mixture consisted of 1 µL of PCR product, 9.6 µL of Hi-Di™ formamide, and 0.4 µL of GeneScan™ 600 LIZ® Size Standard v2.0, prepared according to the GlobalFiler™ guidelines. At least one microliter of allelic ladder was added per injection on the 96-well plate to ensure accurate STR allele sizing.

2.3 Data Analysis and Quality Control

Before capillary electrophoresis, the samples were denatured at 95 °C for 5 minutes and rapidly chilled on ice for 5 minutes. Electrophoresis was conducted using a 36-cm capillary array and POP-4™ polymer (Life Technologies) under standard injection conditions (1.2 kV for 24 seconds). STR data from the electrophoresis output were analyzed using GeneMapper® ID-X Software Version 1.5, following the manufacturer's guidelines, with a detection threshold set at a minimum of 75 RFUs.

For statistical analysis, RStudio was used to perform factorial analysis of variance (ANOVA), with data handling supported by Microsoft Excel. Total RFUs were recorded for homozygous loci, while for heterozygous loci, the peak heights of both alleles were summed. Negative controls included throughout the profiling workflow confirmed the absence of DNA contamination at the quantification and amplification stages, ensuring the integrity of the results.

3 Results

Negative controls processed during the DNA profiling workflow showed no detectable DNA, confirming the absence of contamination during quantification and amplification steps. All analyzed samples yielded either full or partial single DNA profiles, as well as full or partial mixed DNA profiles.

The amount of trace DNA recovered from disposable surgical face masks was significantly influenced by the collection method employed ($p < 0.05$). As shown in **Figure 2**, samples collected using the minitapes (MT) yielded a higher mean DNA concentration (0.41 ng/ μ L) compared to those collected using cotton swabs (CS) (0.17 ng/ μ L). This substantial difference highlights the superior efficiency of MT in trace DNA recovery.

Additionally, the type of DNA profiles recovered was significantly impacted by the collection technique ($p < 0.05$, **Figure 3**). MT sampling produced a higher proportion of full single (FS) and full mixed (FM) DNA profiles compared to CS. Specifically, 27% of the profiles recovered using MT were full single (FS), compared to 21% using CS, while 57% of the profiles recovered using MT were full mixed (FM), compared to 48% with CS. Furthermore, the average signal intensity (RFU) of full single (FS) profiles was notably higher in MT-collected samples (mean RFU: 6194) than in CS-collected samples (mean RFU: 2992). Similarly, analysis of full mixed (FM) DNA profiles revealed that MT recovered more alleles on average (mean: 98 alleles) than CS (mean: 82 alleles).

4 Discussion

The results of this study provide compelling evidence that SceneSafe Fast™ minitapes (MT) outperform cotton swabs (CS) in recovering trace DNA from disposable surgical face masks. The significantly higher DNA yield and improved profile completeness associated with MT align with prior research highlighting the superior performance of adhesive tapes for collecting Touch DNA, particularly from fabric-like surfaces [2,10,26-27].

While this study demonstrated the superior performance of SceneSafe Fast™ minitapes (MT) over Copan cotton swabs (CS) in recovering trace DNA from face masks, it is important to acknowledge that the frequency of mask usage was not documented or controlled. Variability in wearing frequency could influence the amount of deposited DNA, with repeated use potentially leading to higher cell deposition. However, this study employed standardized sampling and recovery protocols across all masks to minimize variability and ensure fair comparisons between the two collection methods. Furthermore, the study's focus was on assessing the relative efficiency of the DNA recovery techniques, which remains valid regardless of individual mask usage frequency.

Figure 2. Comparison of trace DNA recovery from disposable surgical face masks (n = 100) collected using Copan cotton swabs (CS) and SceneSafe Fast™ minitapes (MT). The box plot illustrates the distribution of DNA concentrations for each collection method, highlighting the median, quartiles, and outliers. The mean DNA concentration recovered was significantly higher for MT (0.41 ng/μL) compared to CS (0.17 ng/μL).

Figure 3. Comparison of DNA profiles recovered from disposable surgical face masks (n = 100) using Copan cotton swabs (CS) and SceneSafe Fast™ minitapes (MT). DNA profiles are categorized into four groups: full single (FS), full mixture (FM), partial single (PS), and partial mixture (PM). All partial profiles include alleles from at least nine loci. The figure also highlights the average signal intensity (RFU) per locus for full single (FS) DNA profiles, showing higher RFU values for MT (mean: 6194) compared to CS (mean: 2992). Additionally, the average number of alleles recovered in full mixed (FM) DNA profiles was greater for MT (mean: 98) than for CS (mean: 82), demonstrating notable differences in allele recovery rates between the two methods.

The enhanced efficiency of MT can be attributed to its adhesive properties, which allow it to capture biological material more effectively from porous surfaces. Unlike cotton swabs, which rely on mechanical friction and absorbent capacity, adhesive tapes like MT directly trap epithelial cells and other biological residues embedded in the mask fibers. The study's finding that MT sampling was optimal for up to 16 tape-lifts is consistent with previous studies suggesting that excessive tape-lifting beyond this threshold does not contribute additional recoverable DNA [26,29]. This underscores the importance of methodological optimization in forensic DNA collection to balance efficiency with practicality.

The findings of this study are further supported by Alketbi and Goodwin (2022), who demonstrated that fabric type and sampling area size significantly influence the amount of Touch DNA recovered from clothing [29]. They reported that minitapes are particularly effective for sampling small areas of fabric, while cotton swabs can perform equally well for larger sampling areas. Additionally, the composition of the fabric plays a critical role, with higher DNA recovery observed from polyester-rich materials compared to 100% woven cotton. Given that the disposable surgical face masks used in this study were composed of polypropylene and non-woven fabric, these materials align with the findings of Alketbi and Goodwin (2022), who demonstrated higher DNA recovery from synthetic fiber materials [29]. The adhesive nature of MT is well-suited for small, defined sampling areas, such as the inner surface of a mask, allowing for enhanced recovery of trace DNA.

Further supporting the utility of face masks as a source of forensic DNA, Dash et al. (2023) [43] evaluated the usability of different mask types for DNA evidence. Their findings revealed that portions of the mask covering the mouth region and the ear-pieces are rich sources of genomic DNA, yielding complete autosomal STR profiles in 66.66–96.11% of samples. While no statistically significant differences were found in DNA yields across mask types, their study demonstrated a general trend of higher DNA recovery from cloth masks, followed by N-95 masks and surgical disposable masks. Additionally, they found a positive correlation between the duration of mask wear and DNA yield, emphasizing the importance of wearing frequency as a factor influencing DNA recovery. These insights further underscore the relevance of face masks as a critical evidence type in modern forensic casework and highlight the value of standardized collection methods, such as those evaluated in the present study, to optimize DNA recovery from such substrates.

The study also demonstrates that the type of DNA profile recovered—whether full single (FS), full mixed (FM), or partial—was influenced by the collection method. The higher proportions of FS and FM profiles obtained with MT highlight its potential to maximize the recovery of usable genetic material, even from trace samples. Notably, the superior signal intensity (RFU) observed in MT-collected samples suggests that this method enhances the quality of DNA profiles, thereby improving the likelihood of successful forensic identification. This finding is particularly relevant in cases involving

low-template DNA, where profile quality can be the determining factor in linking a suspect to a crime.

Additionally, the recovery of more alleles in FM profiles using MT further underscores its utility in capturing comprehensive genetic information. This capability is crucial in complex forensic scenarios where mixed profiles often require higher allelic representation to deconvolute individual contributors. By recovering more alleles on average, MT offers an advantage in resolving such cases with greater precision.

The findings also highlight practical considerations for forensic practitioners. The ease of use and minimal preparation required for MT make it a time-efficient alternative to traditional swabbing, especially in high-throughput casework. However, its effectiveness must be evaluated across a wider range of substrates and environmental conditions to fully establish its applicability in diverse forensic contexts. Future research should explore the performance of MT on different types of face masks, such as N95 respirators and cloth masks, as well as its robustness under varying environmental exposures, including humidity, heat, and contamination.

In conclusion, the results strongly support the adoption of minitapes for trace DNA collection from disposable face masks in forensic casework. By providing higher DNA yields and improved profile completeness, MT offers a reliable and efficient alternative to traditional cotton swabbing, especially for porous or fabric-like materials.

5 Conclusion

This study demonstrates that SceneSafe Fast™ minitapes (MT) are significantly more effective than Copan cotton swabs (CS) for recovering trace DNA from disposable surgical face masks. MT yielded higher DNA recovery, produced more complete DNA profiles, and demonstrated greater efficiency in capturing usable genetic material. These findings establish MT as a superior collection method in forensic investigations, particularly for porous or fabric-like surfaces, as exemplified by the widespread use of face masks during the COVID-19 era.

Given the enhanced DNA recovery capabilities of MT, it is strongly recommended as the preferred method for trace DNA collection from face masks in forensic casework. Implementing MT in routine forensic practice can improve the reliability of DNA evidence and facilitate the identification of suspects in criminal investigations. Future

studies should expand on these findings by evaluating the performance of MT on various mask types, including N95 respirators and cloth masks, and under different environmental conditions. Such research will further refine and optimize forensic DNA collection methodologies for diverse applications. Future studies should expand on these findings by evaluating the performance of MT on various mask types, including N95 respirators and cloth masks, as well as under different environmental conditions. Additionally, research could investigate the impact of wearing frequency on DNA deposition and recovery, providing a more nuanced understanding of its role in forensic evidence collection and further optimizing DNA recovery methodologies for diverse applications.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Ethics Statement

This study was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles outlined by the General Department of Forensic Science and Criminology, Dubai Police General Headquarters, Dubai, UAE. The research methodology, including data collection and analysis, was reviewed and approved by the Department to ensure compliance with institutional and international standards for ethical research practices. The study upheld the highest ethical standards to maintain the integrity and reliability of the findings, with the overarching goal of advancing best practices in forensic science.

Author Contributions

S.K.A. Conducted sample collection, performed data analysis, and drafted the main manuscript. **W.G.** Reviewed and revised the manuscript for critical intellectual content. Both authors have read and approved the final version of the manuscript.

Data Availability Statement

Not applicable.

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